

Does inelastic scattering, electron-phonon coupling and the Debye-Waller effect lead to contrast in Scanning Helium Microscopy (SHeM)?

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Scanning Helium Microscopy (SHeM) measures scattered helium intensity from a spot on a surface; conventionally, the interesting content in images comes from the contrast between pixels that has various origins. In the review, apparent observations of chemical contrast in SHeM are considered, particularly the potential for a link with theoretical treatments of inelastic scattering, particularly using the Debye-Waller Factor (DWF). The on-specular reflection form of the DWF cannot be directly applied by itself, but rather, an energy integrated differential reflection coefficient- which includes the DWF and scattering distribution in the scattering transition rate- would be the appropriate measurable for the SHeM. The literature shows that formalisms for the DWF and scattering transition rates would be expected to produce material dependent or chemical contrast; however expressions for a general inelastic transition rate for helium is intractable. The assumptions of the Debye-Waller formalisms suggest that they would not be able to explain the apparent chemical contrast observed. Therefore it will remain to be seen whether the DWF formalism will lead to an improvement in the ray tracing comparisons to data. Chemical contrast would make a significant impact on the applicability of the SHeM technique, especially if it could be understood and predicted for chemical imaging; the Debye Waller mechanism may play a key role in understanding and probing 2D superconductors.

I. INTRODUCTION

The review has four aims. Firstly to introduce scanning helium microscopy (SHeM), explain the critical operating principles and briefly recap scattering and contrast mechanisms in section II. Secondly to review recent reports of apparent chemical contrast observed in the Scanning Helium Microscopy (SHeM) in section III and potential correlation with inelastic scattering mechanism descriptions - particularly Debye-Waller factors in section IV. Thirdly to conclude whether the existing descriptions of the Debye-Waller factor could be used to explain the observations and whether the calculation is tractable V. Finally an outlook for the work is described in section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

SHeM is a spatially resolved microscopy technique that uses a collimated thermal energy, helium beam that scatters from the surface of a sample and a proportion of the helium is detected by the helium detector. By rastering the sample in the beam, an image is produced. Figure 1 shows the schematic geometry used in the technique.

Helium scattering is used for surface science experiments preferentially over x-ray and charged particle methods

FIG. 1: Scanning Helium Microscope (SHeM) schematic from figure 1 of Lambrick *et al.*[1]. Note how the detector cone is fixed relative to the sample surface. The resolution is practically limited by how focused the beam is. Beam width, full width half maxima (FWHM), is typically of the order $1\mu m$. [2] [1]

due to the low energy ($\leq 100meV$) helium beam being exclusively surface sensitive and non-destructive [3] [4]. The sample is not electronically excited nor chemically changed as helium is both neutral and inert.

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There are several key length scales which are relevant to the presented work; the most obvious and perhaps least relevant is that which determines the quoted resolution of the instrument; defined by the FWHM of the beam; typically of order approximately $1\ \mu\text{m}$ [2]. Second is the thermal de Broglie wavelength which for a room temperature beam [2], is $\lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2\pi m k_B T}}$ [5] of $\sim 10^{-11}\text{m}$. Finally, in the current work several models for scattering are considered which have an inherent assumed length scale at which the single harmonic crystal approximation holds. In the review, it will be argued that at the length scale of the helium wavelength, a harmonic single crystal assumption is valid, however it is not valid across the length scale of the FWHM of the beam.

For elastic scattering, the kinetic energy of the atom is unchanged on scattering. If a plane wave is assumed: no change in $\|\mathbf{k}\|$ occurs. Elastic scattering is the dominant process [6] for SHeM and yields on-specular reflection/scattering for a perfectly flat surface.

When imaging a sample, the relative intensity between regions is often the quantity of interest. We define the contrast between two pixels with scattered intensity I_a and I_b :

$$C = \frac{|I_b - I_a|}{|I_b + I_a|} \quad (1)$$

The most striking example of contrast seen in the SHeM is contrast from topography of the surface. The specific

FIG. 2: Topographic contrast at different length scales from figure 4 of Witham *et al.*[7]. Note how smooth surfaces are resolved brighter, and rougher surfaces darker and grainier, with feature size smaller than the beam width. Topographical contrast can be seen from contrast at a resolution that the machine can resolve.

details of topographical features at scales of the order and larger than the FWHM of the beam can be resolved due to topographical contrast. Topographical features at a length scale smaller than the FWHM but larger than the wavelength of helium also scatter intensity away from the specular channel. However the observed signal in the SHeM is only an average effect, such as attenuation

or reinforcement of the signal. The SHeM technique is insensitive to length scales below the helium wavelength. Topography at different length scales is shown in figure 2.

FIG. 3: Schematic representation of diffuse scattering from figure 2 of Lambrick *et al.*[1]. The schematic shows that a range of angles about the specular is accepted by the SHeM detector cone. Therefore the behaviour of the wider scattering distribution rather than only the behaviour of the specular intensity is required to compare theoretical treatments of different scattering mechanisms and experimental measurements.

III. CURRENT RESEARCH ON CHEMICAL CONTRAST

An apparent chemical contrast measured with SHeM has been reported by Barr *et al.* [8] recently. The paper attributes the contrast observed to differences in the atomic character of the regions. Chemical contrast is surprising if we think about it using the classical scattering picture of a ball bouncing off a wall. In classical elastic scattering, it would not matter what the ball (beam atom) is, the walls composition (chemical compound of the surface), or even how hard we throw the ball (beam energy) - we would get specular reflection. Scattered angle equalling the incident angle of the beam. We now consider the experimental observations of Barr *et al.* [8]. Their methods, key logical arguments and conclusions will be highlighted.

The key result reported in Barr *et al.* [8] is figure 4. Clear contrast can be seen between different metals evaporated as thin films on a silicon substrate, definitively demonstrating that a material dependant contrast is present in the observation. However, as will be discussed, that is not a sufficient to claim the instrument has chemical sensitivity since the elemental construction of the sample is not the only difference between samples. It is interesting to note that for most samples there is an enhanced signal compared to the silicon, for platinum

FIG. 4: SHeM micrographs show the University of Newcastle logo patterned using different metals on a silicon substrate. Clockwise from the top left: (a) gold (b) nickel (c) platinum and (d) chromium. Scale bar, $50 \mu m$. Note that the measured scattered intensity from chromium is lower than for gold, when compared to the silicon background. Figure 3 from Barr *et al.*[8]

there no measurable difference and for chromium there is an attenuation of the scattered intensity.

The authors Barr *et al.* [8] use three arguments to discount topographic contrast, the most commonly reported contrast mechanism in SHeM[2].

- The thin metal samples were all prepared using electron beam lithography and thus are inherently self-similar topographically.
- Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was used to show that the root mean square (rms) roughness (height) of the four metal samples and silicon were all of same the order of magnitude, at a scale much smaller than the beam FWHM ($1 \mu m$).
- The contrast seen between the metal and silicon background is weaker than for a part of the same sample with clear topography; and that contrast as a function of perpendicular sample position is inconsistent between the topographic and non-topographically variant parts of the sample.

The arguments rule out explaining the observations with topography which is larger than the AFM's sensitivity, from geometric scattering. The film thickness ($15 nM$) is larger than the thermal de Broglie wavelength of the room temperature helium beam, so no wave effects

would be expected.

The scale below the thermal de Broglie wavelength of helium can be ignored as it would be subatomic. Barr *et al.* [8] then argues that the scale between the beam FWHM and beam de Broglie wavelength would not have caused the contrast observed in figure 4. The AFM results reported [8] the rms roughness (height) of the metals and silicon were all of the order nanometers, with their differences being of the order $10^{-10}m$. There should not be any mechanism where the beam is sensitive to these scales, which are much smaller than the beam FWHM.

Again, there is a mismatch between the scales and the de Broglie wavelength, so wave effects are negligible. The most convincing argument against contrast due to the differences in the roughness of the surfaces is that the rms height of gold was reported as 2.8 nm, whilst silicon was reported to be 1.2 nm- the gold surface found to be rougher than silicon [8]. Rougher surfaces would exhibit greater diffuse scattering away from the specular channel, and would be expected to appear darker in a SHeM image. Exactly opposite as seen for figure 4a. However it should be noted that Barr *et al.* [8] are unclear about the type of AFM ¹ that was used and whether AFM was performed before or after SHeM. If contact AFM was used before, the technique may have altered the surface and the rms roughness reported for the samples may not be representative for figure 4.

It is, however, premature for Barr *et al.* [8] to rule out that the contrast observed is due to differences in topographical features at length scales smaller than the FWHM ($1 \mu m$) between the samples. The contrast observed may be due to other differences in topography of the surface, for example the width of the features at length scales significantly smaller than the lateral resolution ($1 \mu m$). Therefore, Barr *et al.* [8] does not give a convincing argument that the contrast observed is not from topographical features; their argument for chemical contrast hinges on a method of elimination for topographical contrast, yet the list of how the features may differ between from sample to sample, including different adsorbates, were not exhausted.

The relative signal between gold and silicon in figure 5 is much weaker than the silicon and the dust particle. (a)-(d) of figure 5 are images where the scattering pattern is scanned across the detector aperture, capturing information about the scattering distributions of the surface and the dust particle. The contrast between topographic variant part of the sample (the dust particle) and the

¹ A good table of comparing AFM modes can be found at https://www.doitpoms.ac.uk/t1plib/afm/modes_operation.php

scattering pattern weakens from (a)-(d) of figure 5. Consistent contrast when scanning the pattern across the detector aperture would suggest the scattering distribution shapes are the same. Therefore the conclusion from the inconsistent contrast observed is that the scattering distribution shapes of the pattern and the dust are different.

FIG. 5: Micrographs of 15 nm thick patterned layer of gold on top of silicon, partially obscured by a piece of dust. (a) Full image taken with the sample at specular, (b) is at the same position but a section of the image. (c,d) give the same region but at 500 and 1,000 μm further back from the pinhole respectively. Scale bar, 50 μm . Figure 2 from Barr *et al.* [8]

Barr *et al.* [8] attribute the results to inelastic scattering effects. They quote the result of Hulpke [6], which suggests that helium signal that is inelastically scattered is small in comparison with the elastic contribution, 2-3 orders of magnitude lower. The result is consistent with the weak signal of the scattering pattern observed in figure 5. Nevertheless, it is unconvincing that differences between the inelastic scattering of different materials leads to the contrast differences seen in figure 4. The signal that is elastically scattered would swamp the inelastically scattered signal.

Barr *et al.* [8] particularly attribute the apparent observation of chemical contrast to differences between the Debye-Waller factor (DWF) of different materials. The form of the factor they use to describe the variation in specular reflectivity in the presence of inelastic scattering [9] [10] [8] is from Maclaren *et. al* [3].

$$\frac{I}{I_0} = e^{-\frac{24mT(E_i \cos^2 \phi_i + D)}{Mk\Theta_D^2}} \quad (2)$$

The factor in equation 2 resembles a DWF from neutron scattering considerations.

An immediate critique of the DWF used in Barr *et al.* [8] is that it describes specular attenuation only. The schematic in figure 3 shows that the SHeM's detector cone accepts a range of angles about the specular. Therefore information of the wider scattering distribution, rather than just the specular intensity, is

required to compare theory to the measured intensity. Moreover, the observation from figure 5 suggests that there may not be a sharp specular peak due to elastic scattering. The smooth change in contrast with the smooth scanning of the scattering pattern across the detector aperture in images (a)-(d) of figure 5 suggest that the scattering distribution may be broad. A broad distribution would mean the lattice structure of the surface is not regular, leading to no observed diffraction peaks. However, an extremely narrow specular peak would also be consistent with the observations in figure 5, as the detector cone accepts a wide range of angles. More experimental work on the structure of the scattering will need to be done to discern whether the scattering distributions of the samples in Barr *et al.* [8] have specular and other diffraction peaks. It is quite unlikely they do, as the surface lattice is most likely to be irregular with dirt and other adsorbates on it.

The factor describes the fraction of elastic scattering for given incoming and outgoing wavevectors, therefore encoding inelastic scattering. I_0 here is the intensity for a frozen surface [11]. The important dependence in the exponential for SHeM are: M , the surface atomic mass; E_i , the incoming atomic beam energy; T , temperature; Θ_D , the Debye temperature for the material and m , the mass of the beam atoms. Classical models of scattering now seem insufficient and more sophisticated models, which take inelastic processes into account, should be used.

The strong material dependence in the DWF from equation 2 comes from M , D - the potential well depth of the interaction- and Θ_D . Provisional work by Seremet [12] has shown that if the DWF from Manson's 1991 paper [13] is applied on top of a Gaussian broadened specular distribution, the scattering distribution is affected in two ways. The distribution skews away from the specular direction and the intensity of the specular is significantly reduced. The reduction in specular intensity may lead to chemical contrast due to the factor's strong material property dependence in the exponential. However a calculation of the detected intensity by integrating over the solid angle or by ray racing [1] (effectively counting all the helium atoms that enter the detector after scattering) will need to be able to yield a greater and smaller relative intensity, depending on the material, to explain the observations reproduced in figure 4.

The literature is ambiguous when it comes to Debye temperatures for surface science experiments [8] [3]. Jackson [14] also uses a decoupled oscillator model to calculate Debye temperatures, his paper calculates three different Debye temperatures: θ_B (bulk); θ_{\perp} (perpendicular to surface) and θ_{\parallel} (parallel to the surface). There are two different Debye temperatures due to anisotropy at the surface: displacement of the ions parallel to the surface and perpendicular to the surface. The

Debye temperatures used in Barr *et al.* [8] to calculate the contrasts were cited from Ashcroft & Mermin [10], suggesting the bulk Debye temperature values were used.

There is a considerable difference between the bulk, surface parallel and perpendicular Θ_D values. Lyon and Somorjai [15] reported a significantly smaller value (107-118 K) for the surface Θ_D compared to the bulk Θ_D (234 K) for platinum. Castner *et al.* [16] also reported a difference between the perpendicular and parallel surface Θ_D for Rhodium(100). Since the DWF is an exponential factor, small differences will affect which material is predicted to appear brighter in SHeM compared to a different material.

As discussed in the background, helium scattering is exclusively surface sensitive. Therefore surface Debye temperatures should be used in the calculations of Barr *et al.* [8] instead of bulk values.

No calculation of the contrast between the metals were provided by Barr *et al.* [8]. But the DWF for the different materials (assuming pure) from Barr *et al.* [8] can be checked by taking typical scattering values (T = 298K, E = 66 meV, $\phi_i = 45^\circ$, D = 6 meV) from Maclaren *et al.* [3], using the bulk Debye temperatures and material values from Ashcroft & Mermin [10] quoted in table I.

The I/I_0 values calculated and shown in table I are inconsistent with the reported observations. Values calculated suggest that gold would appear the darkest and chromium the brightest, the inverse seen from figure 4. Moreover, the calculated values also disagree with the discussion in Barr *et al.* [8], where they suggest that the contrast seen between nickel and platinum matched the model in Maclaren *et al.* [3]. The contrast calculated for nickel and platinum from table I would be inverted to that seen in experiment.

Nevertheless, Barr *et al.* [8] provides an important consistency check for inelastic scattering, particularly if a Debye-Waller model is used. The on-specular contrast predicted using equation 2 indicates observed contrast would decrease with decreasing beam energy, which is consistent with experiment shown in figure 6 below.

One criticism of the DWFs from theoretical papers [17] [18], which consider the interaction potential to be comprised of an electron-electron and electron-phonon term, is that it is of no direct quantitative use for experimental work on the SHeM; the DWF expressions are often quoted for only for the specular channel. As argued before, on-specular expressions are insufficient for quantitative comparisons in the SHeM. A profile of the scattering distribution about the specular is required.

From the counter arguments presented in this section, Barr *et al.* [8] does not present a persuasive argument

Material	M (u) 3 s.f.	Θ_D (K)	I/I_0 3 s.f.
Gold	197	170 [10]	0.103
Nickel	58.7	375 [10]	0.208
Platinum	195	230 [10]	0.285
Chromium	52.0	460 [10]	0.308
Silicon	28.1	625 [10]	0.307

TABLE I: Table of values for the pure materials from Barr *et al.* [8]. The DWFs I/I_0 from Barr *et al.* [8] are calculated using typical scattering values (T = 298K, E = 66 meV, $\phi_i = 45^\circ$, D = 6 meV) from Maclaren *et al.* [3]. The I/I_0 values calculated are inconsistent with the Barr *et al.* [8] experiment. I/I_0 describes on-specular intensity only and an accurate result for comparison to SHeM experiments would require an expression that includes surface parallel momentum transfer for off-specular. Seremet [12] has shown that if the surfaces have a regular structure, the on-specular intensity still dominates and on-specular expressions would yield an incomplete result, but may give some qualitative insight.

that the observed differences in contrast are not from topographical effects, but rather due to differences in chemical composition of the sample. Inelastic effects may be present in the SHeM, as shown by the energy dependence of the contrast. However contrast due to elastic scattering is expected to swamp inelastic effects. The DWF's functional dependence shows that a Debye-Waller model is able to yield chemical contrast. However a more in depth study of the assumptions of different Debye-Waller models, with differing physics, needs to be done to investigate its applicability to the experiments that Barr *et al.* [8] performed in the SHeM.

In the next section, the assumptions of different Debye-Waller models will be critiqued in the context of the SHeM and the experiments from Barr *et al.* [8]. The tractability of general momentum transfer DWFs, instead of on-specular expressions, will also be explored for the SHeM.

IV. DEBYE-WALLER FACTOR AND INELASTIC SCATTERING

The DWF was historically developed by Debye in 1912 to explain sharp scattering peaks of reduced intensity observed for a crystal at finite temperature; linking the scattered intensity observed at finite temperature, I , (where the lattice is distorted) with the scattered intensity for a frozen crystal lattice, I_0 .

$$I = I_0 e^{-2W} \quad (3)$$

FIG. 6: (a-e) 83, 72, 66, 42, and 21 meV SHeM micrographs of the gold on silicon sample. All images taken with the sample at specular, to investigate the scattering away from specular. The pressure of the beam and temperature of the sample were all kept constant. Barr *et al.* [8] concluded that the dominant contrast displayed by the metal-silicon interface is a consequence of inelastic processes. Figure 4 from Barr *et al.* [8]

The difference between a lattice at finite temperature and frozen lattice is the ion core positions.

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}(t) = \boldsymbol{\rho}_0 + \mathbf{u}(t) \quad [9] \quad (4)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\rho} = \boldsymbol{\rho}_0 \quad [9] \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 describes the lattice position vectors $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ to be fixed and equal to the equilibrium position. Equation 4 includes a time dependent displacement \mathbf{u} which describes the distortion of the lattice due to thermal fluctuations and lattice distortions (phonons).

A. Extending the Neutron Scattering Debye Waller Model

The traditional expression for the DWF (equation 2 of the review) used in equation 2 of Barr *et al.* [8] and in equation 45 of Manson’s 1991 paper [13] can be derived using similar considerations as the derivation of the DWF for neutron scattering [9] [10]. Although chemical contrast based on neutron scattering considerations and the attenuation of the specular intensity is feasible, the assumptions are not valid for the experimental measurement in Barr *et al.* [8]. The physics behind a neutron scattering based model considers an interaction between the helium atom with the displaced ion cores, however the helium beam energy is low therefore an electrostatic interaction between the helium electron density and the surface electron density is expected to dominate instead.

The main assumptions outlined in chapter 2 of Kittel [9] and appendix N of Ashcroft & Mermin [10] for neutron scattering are: Born approximation, where the total wave amplitude is given by a plane wave with a different momentum; and the assumption that the crystal is modelled as an Einstein solid, where the ions behave as independent harmonic oscillators.

The harmonic crystal approximation can be directly applied for the helium scattering case as the assumption is for the sample. The limitation of the Einstein model comes in the low temperature regime (where the temperature is much smaller than the Debye temperature

Θ_D), where the heat capacity of the solid approaches 0 exponentially, which is incorrect [10] [9]. However, for the materials in Barr *et al.* [8], the bulk Debye temperatures are all of the same order of magnitude as room temperature, see table I. The limitation of the harmonic crystal assumption is that samples, such as those in Barr *et al.* [8], are rarely single crystal and often disordered or have adsorbates and dirt on the surface. For helium scattering in the SHeM, at length scales of the helium wavelength ($\sim 10^{-11}m$), it is safe to assume a single harmonic crystal structure because the wavepacket is smaller than typical atomic spacing ($\sim 10^{-10}m$); at scale of the FWHM of the beam, it is not as certain that the single harmonic crystal assumption still holds due to disorder, grain boundaries *etc.* Therefore the breakdown of the assumption for the materials in Barr *et al.* [8] suggests that any Debye-Waller model, which uses the assumption, will not fully explain the experimental measurement in Barr *et al.* [8].

It is not immediately obvious whether the Born approximation can be carried over to helium scattering since the simple s-wave scattering from the fermi-pseudopotential is replaced by more complex scattering from the helium-surface potential, which includes both long-range and short range forces of the electron density of the surface [13]. Section 1.1 of Peierls [19], where a toy model of a square well is used to argue that the shallower and smaller the potential well yields better Born approximation, shows why the interaction potential should be studied before applying the Born approximation. Peierls [19] is consistent with section 7.6.2 of Benedek and Toennies’ book [20] mentions that Born type approximations are probably inadequate for strongly corrugated materials. If the Born approximation is used in good faith, the derivation in Ashcroft & Mermin [10] can be followed. However based on the physics behind neutron scattering, namely where the helium atom scatters off the ion cores, Born type approximations are probably inappropriate for the samples used in Barr *et al.* [8] due to the topographical features at length scales smaller than the FWHM of the beam.

It is safe to assume that the physics behind neutron

scattering does not carry onto helium atom scattering in the SHeM, although the harmonic crystal and Born type approximations are also used in the more sophisticated models that are discussed in the following subsections. As discussed at the start of this section, it is expected that, in the SHeM, the helium atom interacts with the sample surface via an electrostatic interaction. Following section 1.1 of Surprises in Theoretical Physics [19], a static Van der Waals potential well, corresponding to D in equation 2 can be tested to see if the Born approximation is valid. The approximation is valid only if $\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}Ba^2 \ll 1$ [19], where m is the mass of the projectile, B is the well depth- D in our case- and a is the range of the potential ². Using D = 0.38 meV for the He-Cs surface potential as in Campi *et al.* [21] and potential range a equal to the distance of the classical turning point from the surface yields $\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}Ba^2 = 0.726$ and D = 6 meV used in Maclaren *et al.* [3] yields an even larger value of 11.4. Both static Van der Waals potential wells would not give valid Born approximations. However it is important to note that the physical picture is far from static.

The Born approximation can be argued to be valid for helium scattering in the SHeM, for materials with sufficiently free electrons at the surface, such different metals used for imaging in Barr *et al.* [8].

When the helium atom approaches the surface of a metal, the free electrons of the ions redistribute due to the repulsion and also phonon-induced electron density oscillations (EDO) [17], with the redistribution greatest at the surface where the helium is incident on. Section 8.2 of [20] explicitly states the importance of these conduction electrons; the redistribution of surface charge is called *Smoluchowski* smoothing, which softens the He-surface interaction potential. A calculation of a value for the dynamic interaction potential was not found in the literature, it is most probable the Born approximation is assumed as it simplifies all scattering calculations. However if it is assumed that the potential varies slowly spatially, a Thomas-Fermi screening argument can be used to calculate the new pseudo-potential, which comprises the static Van der Waals attraction and repulsion due to the conduction electrons. A derivation can be found in Ashcroft & Mermin [10].

However the silicon substrate, used as the backdrop of figures 4, 5 and 6 from the experiments in Barr *et al.* [8], is an insulator and has topography at length scales smaller than the FWHM ($1\mu m$)- as measured by the AFM [8]. Hence, Born type approximations used in

Debye-Waller theory is expected not to extend to the silicon backdrop of Barr *et al.* [8].

B. Multiple Interactions and General Interaction Potential Debye-Waller Model

Manson [13] does provide a crucial link between the Debye-Waller factor and an experimentally measurable quantity in helium scattering: the differential reflection coefficient $dR/d\Omega_f dE_f^p$, which measures the fraction of the incident helium atoms which are scattered into a final solid angle of $d\Omega_f$ and energy interval dE_f^p . The SHeM does not have energy sensitivity [2], therefore an integrated version over the final state energy should be the measurable quantity in the SHeM. Therefore, the differential reflection coefficient integrated over the helium atom's final state energy should be used for contrast comparisons between the metals, instead of the on-specular Debye-Waller factor, for the contrast experiments in Barr *et al.* [8]. Equation 10 of Manson [13] links the differential reflection coefficient to the transition rate of the scattering event $w(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i)$. Therefore the rest of the current section will critique the additional assumptions considered by Manson [13] for the transition rate, on top of the harmonic approximation and Born type approximations from neutron scattering.

The analysis for the DWF from Manson's 1991 work [13] initially follows the Neutron scattering derivation. A Born type approximation and a single harmonic crystal approximation, used in the neutron scattering model, is also used in this model. Their validity in the SHeM, and particularly for the experiment performed by Barr *et al.* [8] is discussed in the previous subsection. The full derivation won't be discussed, however specific approximations and how the derivation differs from Neutron scattering will be discussed. Manson considers a Hamiltonian for the complete system as:

$$H = H_0 + V \quad (6)$$

$$H_0 = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + H_0^c \quad [13] \quad (7)$$

Manson [13] considers a general interaction potential V , rather than a coupling of the helium atom to the ion cores as described by the neutron scattering model. The final expression for the DW factor, given in equation 45 of the paper [13], can be reformulated to have the same material parameter dependence as the factor quoted by Barr *et al.* [8] (equation 2). The reason for the similarity in the Debye-Waller expressions between the neutron scattering model and the general interaction potential model is because no explicit information of the interaction potential is encoded within

² Technically only holds in the s-wave scattering regime where $ka \ll 1$, which is not the case for Helium-Surface scattering, however it is used to present the idea that the Born approximation should be used cautiously

the neutron scattering or general interaction Debye-Waller models. Equation 25 from Manson's paper [13] shows the lack of interaction dependence in the Debye-Waller factor in the model, the expression is given below.

$$W_\kappa(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_{\alpha, \alpha'=1}^3 k_\alpha k_{\alpha'} \sum_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \frac{\hbar}{NM_\kappa \omega_\nu(\mathbf{Q})} e_{\alpha, \kappa}(\mathbf{Q}, \nu) \times (n_\nu(\omega_\nu(\mathbf{Q})) + 1/2) \quad [13] \quad (8)$$

The expression describes the attenuation of the scattered signal due to the displacement of the κ th surface atom, with mass M_κ . \mathbf{Q} is the parallel wave vector, ν is a discrete quantum number for the surface phonon modes and continuous for bulk modes; $e_{\alpha, \kappa}(\mathbf{Q}, \nu)$ is the polarization vector of the corresponding mode, $\omega_\nu(\mathbf{Q})$ is the mode frequency, and $n_\nu(\omega_\nu(\mathbf{Q}))$ is the Bose-Einstein distribution. No information about the nature of the interaction potential is included.

A thermal, ensemble average over the crystal states (denoted by the angle brackets $\langle \langle \dots \rangle \rangle$) was taken for the particle transition rate (for the helium atom transitioning from a state $\mathbf{k}_i \rightarrow \mathbf{k}_f$). The averaging represents the lack of perfect information about the system due to thermal fluctuations. The DWF is then defined using the thermal, ensemble average as:

$$2W(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i, T) = \langle \langle n | (\mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{u}(t))^2 | n \rangle \rangle \quad [13] \quad (9)$$

Where $|n\rangle$ is the crystal eigenstate, $\mathbf{q} \equiv (\mathbf{K}, \Delta k)$ where \mathbf{K} is the wavevector of the He atom parallel to the surface, and Δk is the change in He wavevector normal to the surface.

Equation 6 has two parts, the unperturbed Hamiltonian H_0 which comprises of the free particle Hamiltonian and the unperturbed Hamiltonian for the crystal. The perturbation comes from the interaction potential V which couples the Helium projectile to the solid. The total eigenstate of H_0 is a product state between the free particle state for the Helium and energy eigenstate of the crystal unperturbed Hamiltonian. Manson [13] then defines a transition operator $\mathcal{T} = V + VG^+\mathcal{T}$ where G^+ is the retarded green's function. The transition operator is an operator representation of the integral equation for scattering amplitudes which yields the Lippman-Schwinger equation described on pages 390-391 in Sakurai [22]. The transition operator thus describes all possible interactions of the helium atom with the interaction potential. The transition operator is particularly useful for describe scattering from a collective system of matter, such as a dynamic crystal.

There are two additional major assumptions in the derivation, apart from the harmonic crystal and Born type approximation:

1. First assumption is that the total transition operator, \mathcal{T} , can be written as a pairwise sum of transition operators for each surface unit cell (denoted by l) and its constituents (denoted by k).

$$\mathcal{T} = \sum_{l, \kappa} \tau^{l, \kappa} \quad [13] \quad (10)$$

$\tau^{l, \kappa}$ is the transition operator for the κ^{th} constituent in the l^{th} surface unit cell. The approximation ignores many-body forces, but includes multiple scattering from the surface unit cell and its units.

2. The second assumption is the unit cells are all identical and the surface is perfectly periodic, described the following equation:

$$\mathcal{T}_{\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i}(t) = \sum_{l, \kappa} e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot (\mathbf{r}_{l, \kappa} + \mathbf{u}_{l, \kappa}(t))} \tau_{\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i}^{\kappa} \quad [13] \quad (11)$$

$r_{l, \kappa}$ is the equilibrium position of the κ^{th} constituent in the l^{th} surface unit cell, and $u_{l, \kappa}(t)$ is the corresponding instantaneous displacement from equilibrium. Time t is from the interaction between the atom and the surface and the DWF is defined at the instant of interaction $t \rightarrow 0$. The major approximation of periodicity is an adequate one for all neutron scattering, due to the underlying periodicity of the ions. However the interaction for helium atoms are between the surface and atomic electron densities, and between the surface electron density with the ion cores. Therefore for helium scattering, the approximation is only good for processes with low-energy, long wavelength phonons. Moreover, when the periodicity is broken, such as the boundary between two materials, or amorphous materials, the DWF derived in Manson [13] will not be valid.

Taking different number of phonons corresponds to expanding the transition rate to different orders and the full derivation can be found in Manson's paper [13].

Equation 38 of Manson [13], equation 12 below:

$$w(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) = \frac{N}{\hbar^2} |\tau_{fi}|^2 e^{-2W(\mathbf{k})} S(\mathbf{K}, \omega) I(\mathbf{K}, \omega) \quad (12)$$

shows that the helium atom transition rate due to scattering is the product of: a form factor $|\tau_{fi}|^2$ comprised of the matrix elements of the transition operator; a Debye-Waller factor; a structure factor $S(\mathbf{K}, \omega)$ ³ and an energy exchange factor $I(\mathbf{K}, \omega)$. The product of the form factor (containing information about the interaction potential) and the structure factor (encoding

³ Information about structure factors can be found in the appendix

information about the structure of the surface of the sample) will describe a scattering distribution for the helium atoms. No information about the scattering distribution is encoded by the DWF, it only corrects for displacement of the surface atoms by attenuating the distribution in the expression of the transition rate [13]. Therefore, it is unlikely that the DWF, by itself, will be useful to model measured scattered intensities, which was done in Barr *et al.* [8]. For the comparison of the I/I_0 factor in Barr *et al.* [8] to be justifiable, the scattering distributions of helium for the different materials would have to be the same, which is improbable.

However, the Debye-Waller factor modelled by Manson (equation 45 in Manson [13]) is always the same for any number of phonon modes, and is independent of the mode. Moreover, as discussed before, the DWF contains no explicit information about the interaction potential. It is a little difficult to believe that exciting a different number of surface and sub-surface phonon modes [23] of with different dispersion relations, by coupling to different interaction potentials, yields the same attenuation factor in the transition rate. Manson's model [13] will numerically be able reproduce chemical contrast, however it is uncertain whether it will accurately model the scattered helium intensity with samples, for which the harmonic and Born type approximations are valid, due to doubt about the DWF- as discussed before. As discussed in the previous subsection, Manson's model [13] probably does not explain the experimental measurements performed in the SHeM by Barr *et al.* [8], as a harmonic crystal assumption is used.

C. Phonon Mode-dependent Debye-Waller Model with Thermal Ensemble Average Before Single Phonon Approximation

Sklyadneva *et al.* [17] was able to describe the pseudo-potential for the helium atom, described in Manson [13] as a general interaction potential V , in two parts: an electron-electron interaction between the atom electron density and the surface electron density; an electron-phonon interaction, the strength which is characterised by the mass-enhancement factor λ . The supplementary material in Sklyadneva *et al.* [17] shows that the DWF can be related to the electron-phonon coupling matrix, which describes the strength of the electron-phonon interaction in the material.

Even though the model would likely not be able to explain the experimental observations in Barr *et al.* [8], due to the harmonic crystal assumption, the mode dependent attenuation from the DWF is encouraging for describing inelastic helium scattering from single crystal, clean materials in the SHeM. It should be noted that in the supplementary material of Sklyadneva *et al.* [17], the

authors suggest that the DWF is practically unity and should be neglected. Although the statement would be consistent with Hulpke's [6] description that elastic scattering dominates inelastic processes, until the scattering profile of the samples of Barr *et al.* [8] in the SHeM is investigated further, it is premature to neglect inelastic effects. The beam energy dependence of contrast, shown in figure 6, is a promising sign for detecting inelastic processes in the SHeM- albeit not without its doubts- as discussed in section III.

FIG. 7: Incident helium atom in state of wavevector \mathbf{k}_i is inelastically scattered into a final state of wavevector \mathbf{k}_f by the overlap vertex I_F and creates a phonon of wavevector $\Delta \mathbf{K}$ (we use \mathbf{q}) and branch index ν via a virtual electron-hole pair of states. I_F characterises the electron-electron interaction and $g(\Delta \mathbf{K}, \nu)$ characterises the electron-phonon interaction. The inelastic scattering mechanism comes about when the energy and momentum of the scattered helium changes due to an exchange in energy with the phonon gas of a solid through oscillations of the electron density at the surface, *electron-density oscillations* Figure 1 from Manson *et al.* [18].

Figure 7 is a schematic representation of the pseudo-potential, an electron-hole pair may be created to transfer the change momentum in momentum to unit cells several layers deeper, where the quantised phonon modes better match the energy and momentum difference. There is good evidence that phonons are excited several layers below the surface such as in the quantum sonar effect section of Benedek *et al.* [23] and in Campi *et al.* [21]. Manson *et al.* [18] mentions that the momentum transfer dependence in the analysis is substantially more complex than the quadratic dependence used in neutron scattering [10] [9]. The complex dependence on the momentum transfer, alongside the complication due to the attractive adsorption well is introduced through the presence of distorted atomic wave functions for the He atom's motion normal to the surface.

A good question to ask is whether a quasiparticle formalism is, in fact, appropriate for certain materials. Quasiparticles are not well defined if the mean free path of the quasiparticle is smaller than the quasiparticle

wavelength [24]; no notion of a quasiparticle wavepacket can be formed. Zhang *et al.* [24] has shown that for strongly correlated materials called "bad metals", doped complex insulators with many phonon bands and also strong electron-phonon interactions, electrons and phonons cannot be treated separately. In these materials, the Mott-Ioffe-Regel limit [24] to the DC resistivity is broken above certain temperatures. A similar analysis should be performed on the samples in Barr *et al.* [8] to see whether a quasiparticle regime is valid for an electron-phonon model to inelastic scattering, such as the one in Sklyadneva *et al.* [17] and Manson *et al.* [18].

The Hamiltonian in equations 6 and 7 are changed by Sklyadneva *et al.* [17]. A Ebsjerg-Nørskov potential term ($An(\mathbf{r})$ [17] [18]) is added to the unperturbed Hamiltonian, where $n(\mathbf{r})$ is the surface charge density and A is a constant. The perturbation is now the phonon-induced modulation to the potential $V = A\delta n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ [17] [18] at the classical turning point for He. The distorted wave functions of the helium decay rapidly past the classical turning point. We can qualitatively argue why there is a change in surface electron density due to the perturbation. Similar to Manson's 1991 paper [13] and Neutron scattering [9] [10], Sklyadneva *et al.* [17] takes the thermal, ensemble average *before* a Taylor expansion to a n^{th} order for n-phonon modes, which yields a DWF that is ignorant to the number of phonon modes. Again it is nonphysical to have the I/I_0 fraction independent from the number of phonon modes.

D. Phonon Mode-dependent Debye-Waller Model with Thermal Ensemble Average After Single Phonon Approximation

Manson's 2016 paper [18] reported a phonon-mode dependent effective DWF. The derivation is almost identical to Sklyadneva *et al.* [17], however the thermal, ensemble average is taken *after* a one-phonon approximation⁴. Taking the average after the one-phonon approximation means all configurations of the crystal is weighted and taken into account for an excitation of one phonon mode, similar to the schematic in figure 7.

With similar arguments about the harmonic approximation from the three previous sections, the Debye-Waller model from Manson's 2016 paper [18] will likely not be able to explain the contrast observed in Barr *et al.* [8]. The phonon-mode dependent effective DWF described by equation 4 of Manson [18] includes a term involving the interaction potential (as shown in equation D1) is juxtaposed with equation 9 which does not

involve the interaction term. The additional interaction dependence in the DWF suggests that the transition rate for Manson's mode dependent model [18] will have more material dependent parameters than his model [13] which considers the interaction potential only generally. Therefore it is probable that the measurable for the SHeM, the differential reflection coefficient integrated over final state energy $dR/d\Omega_f$, will have a stronger material dependence for Manson's phonon mode dependent model [18] than the general interaction potential model from Manson [13].

Manson *et al.* [18] produces the following expression for the effective DWF for on-specular scattering (assuming no change in momentum parallel to the surface), assuming one phonon mode is excited and in the limit of high temperature:

$$2W^{eff}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) \cong 4N(E_F) \frac{m}{m_e^*} \frac{E_{iz}}{\phi} \lambda k_B T_S \quad [18] \quad (13)$$

$N(E_F)$ is the density of states at the Fermi Surface for the surface electrons, m_e^* is the effective mass of the electron (at the Fermi surface), E_{iz} is the incident beam energy, ϕ is the workfunction for the material, λ is the electron-phonon (e-p) coupling constant or mass-enhancement factor (which describes the strength of interaction between the electron density and the ion cores) and T_S is the surface temperature.² Even though equation 13 is successful in Helium Atomic Scattering (HAS), see figure 8, it is inappropriate for the SHeM, which accepts angles other than the specular channel- as discussed in section III.

FIG. 8: Figure 2 from Manson *et al.* [18]. Debye-Waller plots of the specular intensity versus surface temperature for He atom scattering from Sb(111) and Bi(111). More information on experimental and theoretical values of λ in the literature is discussed in the appendix.

⁴ The reason for the one-phonon approximation and other insights for Manson's [18] derivation is explored in the appendix

A general expression for the effective DWF which includes a change in the parallel momentum of the He atom

is derived by the review, the details are left for the appendix.

$$2W^{eff}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(E_F) \frac{T_S}{\phi} \frac{m}{m_e^*} \sum_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \lambda_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \Delta E(\mathbf{Q}) \quad (14)$$

ΔE is the change in energy of the helium atom or the energy of the phonon of momentum \mathbf{Q} parallel to the surface and $\lambda_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu}$ is the mode-specific e-p coupling constant. It should be reiterated that the mode dependent model by Sklyadneva *et al.* [17] and Manson [18] would unlikely be able to explain the experimental measurement from Barr *et al.* [8]. For comparisons to contrast measurements of a clean crystal (where the single harmonic crystal assumption is most valid) in the SHeM, equation should be used in the single phonon inelastic transition rate described in equation 8 of Manson [18]. Equation 10 of Manson [13] can be used to link the transition rate to the differential reflection coefficient $dR/d\Omega_f dE_f^p$ and integrated over the final state energy E_f^p to yield an observable in the SHeM. However, a key point is that the general momentum transfer DWF from equation 14 and the single phonon inelastic transition rate $w_{DWB A}^{(1)}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i)$ would not be tractable to calculate due to the weighted sum of the mode-specific components of λ , which are derived from the e-p coupling matrix, and the change in energy of the helium beam ΔE as a function of phonon mode excited. These two terms are not readily accessible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, the DWF alone is insufficient to model chemical contrast; a measurable in the SHeM- the energy integrated differential reflection coefficient- which includes the Debye-Waller factor in the scattering transition rate should be used in comparisons of theory to SHeM measurements. The on-specular DWFs quoted in theoretical papers [8] [3] [13] [18] are not directly useful for quantitative comparisons for SHeM experiments as the SHeM detector accepts angles about specular. However there is promise that Debye-Waller models would be able to model material dependent chemical contrast in the SHeM, with Manson's mode dependent model [18] the most promising. Yet, the general momentum transfer DWF from equation 14 and the single phonon inelastic transition rate $w_{DWB A}^{(1)}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i)$ would not be tractable to calculate due to the inaccessibility of the e-p coupling matrix for each material, and the change in energy of the helium beam ΔE as a function of phonon mode excited.

It is likely that the assumptions used in the different Debye-Waller models, such as Born type approximations and a harmonic crystal assumption can not be reliably applied to the samples used in Barr *et al.* [8], therefore making the Debye-Waller models impractical for ex-

plaining the contrast seen in figure 4. Furthermore, it is unclear whether the samples have well defined quasiparticles, which is assumed for all the Debye-Waller models- allowing a perturbative expansion for multiphonon processes. It is likely that the contrast seen in Barr *et al.* [8] will be explained by topographical effects, which swamp the inelastic contributions from helium scattering. More work on investigating the details of the helium scattering distributions is required before accepting an inelastic explanation.

VI. OUTLOOK

It is important that the structure of the scattering distributions for the samples in Barr *et al.* [8] is investigated. Diffraction peaks that are attenuated, with increased intensity between the peaks due to incoherent scattering, would be a supportive case to continue to use Debye-Waller models. However if the scattering distribution is broad and without a specular peak, due to an irregular surface lattice, it would strongly suggest that the Debye-Waller factor would not explain the contrast observed by Barr *et al.* [8].

It would be feasible to conduct a proof of concept study of the DWF's effect in SHeM 'images' as a function of surface temperature since there is a clear dependence to the inelastic scattering using chemical contrast and changing the surface temperature is a commonly available function of surface science experiments.

A check on whether the samples in Barr *et al.* [8] have well defined quasiparticles can be done by measuring the DC resistivity of the samples as a function of temperature and seeing whether the resistivity breaks the Mott-Ioffe-Regel limit for electrons. If it does, it will suggest that there are no well defined quasiparticles (electron and hole quasiparticles or phonons) and the Debye-Waller theories do not model the materials well. Another measurement that can be made for these samples is the inverse thermal diffusivity data as a function of temperature for these models as in figure 1 of Zhang *et al.* [24].

One incredibly interesting question the treatment of the e-p mass coupling raises is if inelastic scattering in the SHeM could help tell us something about superconductivity. Electron-Phonon coupling is important in superconducting theory, notably BCS theory, where the e-p coupling potential comes into the superconducting transition temperature T_c [25]. The ratio $\lambda_{Pb}/\lambda_{Bi}$ is reported to be 1.35 in bulk. Whereas that reported from the DWF is 0.75 for Bi(111) against a thin 7 Monolayer(ML)-Pb(111) [18]. The ratio is particularly interesting as Pb is a known bulk superconductor, whereas Bi is not. With reduced dimensionality such as in a 2D material, or a thin film- Bi(111) becomes

a superconductor, whereas Pb(111) has its transition temperature lowered- making it less of a superconductor. Using the ratio observation for Pb(111) and Bi(111) and the knowledge that stronger e-p coupling is often attributed to aiding superconductivity, the SHeM could be used to measure the ratio of mass enhancement factors/ e-p coupling constants for novel materials against known thin film superconductors. Hence the SHeM may be able to test for new thin film, 2-D and surface superconducting candidates. An extension on the investigation of the superconductivity of thin film lead would be the measurement of e-p coupling constant λ as a function of the number of atomic layers. Chiang [26] suggests the superconducting transition temperature varies in an oscillatory manner with the number of atomic layers of lead, until the bulk regime. It would be interesting to see if a similar variation in λ can be observed.

Polaron theory and polaron models for high temperature superconducting theory, where the quasi particle is reformulated from the strong interaction between electrons and phonons [27], may be able to be probed using helium scattering. Polaron superconductivity is different from BCS theory because the current is mediated via the polaron, rather than a cooper pair. Both an electric field and thermal energy is required for the polaron to hop from lattice site to lattice site to conduct. Polaron theory may be a candidate for a high temperature superconductivity theory in unconventional superconductors.

The role of the Debye-Waller factor and inelastic scattering in scanning helium microscopy will continue to become essential, but only for clean, regular surfaces. It may play a key role in understanding and probing 2D superconductors, that are in vogue currently.

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Appendix A: Structure Factor

There are two different mathematical expressions for structure factor.

The first, $F_{hkl} = \sum_j f_j \exp(-i\boldsymbol{\rho}_j \cdot \mathbf{G})$ [9] is proportional to the scattering amplitude and is used for perfect crystals. hkl are miller indices for the scattering plane, the sum is over the atoms. f_j is the atomic form factor, which encodes the scattering power

of the j^{th} atom. $\boldsymbol{\rho}_j$ is the position vector of the j^{th} atom and \mathbf{G} is the reciprocal lattice vector of the crystal.

The second, $S(\mathbf{q})$, where \mathbf{q} is the momentum transfer, is proportional to the scattering amplitude [10]. The static structure factor, $S(\mathbf{q})$, can be obtained by integrating the dynamic structure factor $S(\mathbf{q}, \omega)$ over ω . The integral over ω can be viewed as including both the inelastic and elastic scattering contributions. The dynamic structure factor can be viewed as the space-time Fourier transform of the density(operator)-density(operator) correlation function $\frac{1}{N} \langle \hat{n}(\mathbf{r}, t) \hat{n}(\mathbf{r}', 0) \rangle_T$ [28]. The density-density correlation function is the probability of finding a particle (from the surface) at \mathbf{r} and at time t when there is one at \mathbf{r}' at time $t = 0$.

The exposition in the University of Cambridge, Part III TQM notes [29] explains that $S(\mathbf{q}, \omega)$ gives the rate at which a system makes transitions that impart energy ω and momentum \mathbf{q} in the presence of a perturbation H_{pert} . A more in depth derivation is given in section 3.17 of Abrikosov *et al.*'s [30] Methods of Quantum Field Theory in Statistical Physics. The obvious assumption is that the perturbation is small compared to the system Hamiltonian [31]. In our case, the interaction potential $\mathcal{V}(\mathbf{r})$ of the helium and surface would need to be small compared to the original energy of the helium atom in the beam.

By considering the scattering of a helium wavepacket off the surface, \mathbf{q} is the momentum transfer of the helium, and ω can be viewed as the change in energy of the wavepacket in units of \hbar . It clear to see that the $\omega = 0$ contribution is the elastic scattering part, and non zero ω correspond to the inelastic scattering.

Appendix B: Experimental and Theoretical values for the e-p coupling constant/ Mass enhancement factor λ

The values of the electron-phonon (e-p) coupling constant from Helium Atomic Scattering (HAS) λ_{HAS} was found using equation 11 from Manson *et al.*[18]. These values are in agreement with other quoted values for the mass-enhancement factor λ for the strength of e-p coupling in the material. However it is noted by Manson *et al.* [18] that there can be significant variants in reported values, with the electron-phonon coupling constant for inelastic scattering lower than other sources due to only a select set of phonon modes are accessible via an inelastic mechanism. It should be noted that the values of λ from other experimental data that do not involve inelastic scattering, or the same modes may yield inconsistent results. For example if we compare the value of λ for Bi(111) reported by Tamtögl *et al.* [32] and that from Manson *et al.* [18], if we take the exponential of the ratio

of them, we get a factor of about 10. Small differences in λ will be blown up due to the exponential. However recently there has been work done by Benedek *et al.* [11] on performing the same calculation that was done in Manson *et al.* [18] to calculate bulk values of λ for a material. By calculating λ for single and multiple layers of alkali metals and Pb on Cu(111) and extrapolating the results to large thickness gives a result that agrees favourably with known bulk values.

Appendix C: Derivation insights and the one-phonon approximation in Manson *et al.* [18]

The pseudopotential that is considered comprises a short range potential due to increase in kinetic energy due to the presence of the helium atom and a longer range term due to the electrostatic polarization of the He. Section 8.2 of [20] argues that the second term is ignored as the long range term largely screens the electrostatic potential between ion cores and the polarized atom. The interaction potential comes from repulsive force between the surface electron density and the helium's electron density $n(\mathbf{r})$.

The surface electron density is found by the sum of the modulus squared of the electron wave functions of the occupied states, that contribute at the classical turning point, over parallel wave vector \mathbf{K} and band index n . By discretizing the surface into infinitesimal squares, the squares where the helium atom is incident on and there is the repulsive interaction potential has its electron states raised in energy. Here I have used an argument similar to that in Thomas-Fermi screening, where the spatial variation of the potential is assumed to be much larger than that of the wavelength of the electron states [10]. It is clear that the Fermi energy of the states in these squares increases, and to minimise energy- only the free states near the Fermi energy move outwards away from the helium atom, which is the reason why the density of states at the Fermi energy appears in the effective DWF in equations 13 and IV D.

The one phonon approximation stems from quantum field theory. Higher number of phonons are not considered as it would result in a greater number of vertices compared to that in figure 7. These higher order Feynman diagram would have smaller and smaller contributions, especially since a greater number of propagators would be required to describe the electron-hole pair. A greater number of propagator terms would also add to the suppression for the higher order terms [33].

Appendix D: Original derivation for general effective DWF for one-phonon inelastic scattering

The following section derives an original general expression for the effective DWF following the arguments from Manson *et al.* [18].

$$2W^{eff}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) = 4 \sum_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \frac{\hbar}{NM\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu}} \times \left| \sum_{\alpha}^3 \frac{I_F(\mathbf{Q})}{\langle \chi_{k_{iz}}(z) | n_{\mathbf{Q}}^{eff}(T_s, z) | \chi_{k_{fz}}(z) \rangle} \frac{1}{E_{K,n}^{el} - E_{K-Q,n'}^{el}} \sqrt{\frac{2NM\omega_{\Delta K, \nu}}{\hbar}} g_{n,n'} \right|^2 \left[n_{BE}(\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu}) + \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad (D1)$$

Equation D1 comes from combining 4,5 and 6 from Manson *et al.* [18]. \mathbf{Q} is the surface parallel wavevector for the phonon; ν is the branch index for the phonon; n and n' are the perpendicular wavevector for the He atom before and after scattering respectively; α are a cartesian index; N is the number of atoms; $I_F(\mathbf{Q})$ is the overlap integral matrix element giving the surface electron density, interacted by the distorted He atomic wavefunctions $\chi(z)$ for motion normal to the surface; $n_{\mathbf{Q}}^{eff}(T_s, z)$ gives the effective electron density which causes repulsion; $g_{n,n'}$ is the electron-phonon coupling matrix which describes the direction and strength of coupling and $n_{BE}(\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu})$ is the Bose-Einstein distribution for Bosons.

By substituting equation 7 from Manson *et al.* [18]; using the Grimvall approximation $E_{K,n}^{el} - E_{K-Q,n'}^{el} = \hbar\omega_{\Delta K, \nu}$; using conservation of momentum, where the change in surface parallel momentum for the helium is converted to the surface parallel momentum of the phonon ($\Delta K = Q$); assuming rough isotropy (particularly over the two surface directions) to remove the sum over the cartesian components and considering exponential decay $exp-2\kappa z$ for the electron density at the He-atom turning point, with $\kappa = \sqrt{2m_e^* \phi / \hbar}$, where ϕ is the workfunction and m_e^* is the electron effective mass- we get:

$$2W^{eff}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(E_F) \frac{1}{\phi m_e^*} \sum_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \lambda_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} |\mathbf{Q}|^2 \times \left| \frac{I_F(\mathbf{Q})}{\langle \chi_{k_{iz}}(z) | n_{\mathbf{Q}}^{eff}(T_s, z) | \chi_{k_{fz}}(z) \rangle} \right|^2 \left[n_{BE}(\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu}) + \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad (D2)$$

Manson *et al.* [18] states that the ratio between the electron-electron overlap integral matrix element I_F and the distorted wave matrix elements of the repulsive potential is nearly unity [18]. An example they give is for weakly corrugated metals. By also considering the high temperature limit ($n_{BE} \rightarrow k_B T_S / \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu}$) and exponential decay for the electron density at the He-atom turning point, we get the following for the general momentum

transfer DWF. These assumptions leads to the expression from equation 14:

$$2W^{eff}(\mathbf{k}_f, \mathbf{k}_i) \sim \mathcal{N}(E_F) \frac{T_S}{\phi} \frac{m}{m_e^*} \sum_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \lambda_{\mathbf{Q}, \nu} \Delta E(\mathbf{Q}) \quad (\text{D3})$$

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